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1. Introduction

The eRImote project (European Research Infrastructures - Pathway to Improved Resilience through Digital and Remote Access) aims to engage a broad stakeholders' community beyond the consortium partners in order to explore and assess the different relevant aspects of remote access service provision including technical and financial requirements, advantages and drawbacks as well as avenues for further exploitation. The consortium has been tasked to identify strategies and solutions to enable the transition to more remote and digital access to Research Infrastructure (RI) across all fields of research services and be inclusive in terms of typology of RIs and services. The initial phase of the project is therefore focusing on the identification and engagement of relevant stakeholders in view of their participation in the project activities.

The purpose of this deliverable is to identify and describe the different stakeholders' groups and outline an *Outreach and Dissemination Plan* for the consortium to be delivered through diverse communication channels over the 30-month duration of the project. The deliverable is part of Work Package 5 – Outreach and Dissemination which aims to support the other work packages in ensuring a broad outreach to stakeholders and subsequent dissemination of results.

The work presented in the deliverable was mostly done by ESF with contributions from all partners as well as input from WP3.

2. Stakeholders mapping

2.1. Stakeholder groups

The stakeholder mapping work carried out by ESF aims to precisely identify the different target groups for the engagement, outreach and dissemination activities. In general terms, these include:

- The 12 partners of the eRImote project and their respective networks
- The wider Research Infrastructure (RI) community – European and globally including management, RI staff and users
- The broad scientific community in different research fields of activity
- Industry partners – as providers of solutions and users of services
- Policymakers and funders – key to the dissemination of the Green Paper at the conclusion of the project.

This initial deliverable focuses on RI stakeholders as they are the ones that need to be addressed as a priority during the first phase of the project.

The eRImote project has identified **six main categories of services** which can be delivered via remote access. These are related to access to physical facilities/instrumentation or other types of resources that can be digital or human. Depending on the category, the specificities of the process and respective stakeholders may vary.

We have therefore identified, thanks to inputs gathered during the workshops, a number of **processes** related to remote access service provision. These are schematically represented below and will be further defined during the course of the project.

Finally, the different **stakeholders** have been detailed depending on the type of activity they are involved in and their interest in remote access provision. For some of them (i.e. RI projects), a detailed mapping has been carried out, while for others such as industry and users, more information needs to be gathered (namely through tasks 5.2 and 5.3 starting in M6).

Figure 1 presents these different aspects and how they are interlinked in a schematic way. The next steps in the project will be to further investigate and illustrate these interlinkages with concrete examples, describing success factors and challenges. What can be observed from this preliminary analysis is that:

- Remote access to physical instrumentation and equipment seems to imply the largest number of processes that need to be set-up, thus, possibly increasing costs and efforts needed for its implementation.
- A number of processes rely heavily on the scientific, technical, IT and data management staff which may also increase the workload and costs of the delivery of the service.

Figure 1. Stakeholder groups in relation to categories of services and processes with an indication of links between them.

2.3. Research Infrastructures mapping by category

The MERIL project¹ has identified over 1,000 RIs and has been used as a source to provide an initial picture of those who reported to offer remote access. Since the information on the access type was not compulsory in the MERIL database, only a limited number of entries contained this information and could therefore be analyzed as reported below.

Figure 3. Categories of Research infrastructures offering remote and mail-in access as included in the MERIL database (Source: <https://portal.meril.eu/>). The names of the corresponding RIs are listed in Annex 2.

¹ The MERIL-2 project has ended in August 2019

Even though the information is available only for 31 research infrastructures (see Annex 2 for full list), the data is indicative of the fact that remote/mail-in access is offered by a variety of different categories of RIs covering all scientific domains. This information is important in order to guide the dissemination and outreach strategy that needs to remain inclusive and open to be able to capture the diversity of RIs and their services that may have an interest in the project activities and its outcomes.

2.4. Services mapping

There is a large and increasing number of RI catalogs of services currently being developed throughout Europe. The CatRIS project has analyzed over 40 different catalogs and provided the corresponding assessments in terms of content and functionalities². There is evidence that there is a number of services included in these catalogs that are offered, at least to some extent, remotely. However, only a few catalogs (such as the ones provided by INSTRUMENT, EMBRC, ACTRIS, ENVRI-FAIR, EMBL) mention it explicitly.

The CatRIS catalogue³ allows to filter services according to the access type (physical, remote/mail-in or virtual) and therefore can provide a snapshot of available remote services. RIs listed in the CatRIS database have indicated 211 services that are delivered remotely or via mail-in presented in figure 4. As previously named, a similar trend that remote access service provision spans all ESFRI-domains is observed.

² https://project.catris.eu/uploads/ficheiro_D4.1_final_submitted.pdf

³ <https://www.portal.catris.eu/home>

Figure 4 Research infrastructures offering remote and mail-in services. Source: <https://www.portal.catris.eu/home>. The size of the square is proportional to the number of services categories (as defined by the eRImôte project see Figure 1) offered via remote access, the maximum being six. The full names of the RIs are listed in Annex 3.

A more thorough analysis of the remote services landscape will be performed within WP3 and WP4 in the next phases of the project in order to obtain a more comprehensive picture of the overall RI landscape.

3. Outreach and Dissemination Strategy

In order for the dissemination strategy to be effective and to provide tangible results, a well-structured methodology should be adopted in terms of:

- Defining the **main objective** of the dissemination strategy, i.e. promoting the eRImote ideas, objectives and results to all potential stakeholders.
 - *what is the main goal*: encouraging the RI stakeholder community to transition to remote access, see section 3.1.
- Defining **what will be disseminated**; the dissemination “products” or message.
 - *what will be communicated*: both the expected outcomes of using remote access service provision of RIs, and seeking input from the stakeholders on how this should be implemented, see Figure 5 in section 3.1.
- Identifying the **target groups** for dissemination, i.e. to disseminate the work carried out, knowledge produced and results achieved to the wider possible audience.
 - *who is the audience*: the RI stakeholder community, see section 2.
- Establishing the **appropriate source** for the dissemination activities.
 - *How to communicate*: workshops, conferences, consultation, expert group meetings, policy event, reports, articles and others, see section 3.2.
- Raising public awareness on the project achievements through the **most suitable means** for communicating with the respective target groups.
 - *What media is used to communicate through*: newsletters, websites, social media and others, see section 3.3.

3.1. Key messages

The purpose of this outreach and dissemination plan is to disseminate the core message of the project to the target audience. In this case, the question that aims to be answered is “Why should a RI/user be interested in the project?”

The expected outcomes of the project are as follows:

- Increased resilience of research infrastructures during crisis
- Reduced ecological footprint of research infrastructure activities
- Wider access to research infrastructures and enlargement of their user base
- Increased efficiencies of access to/service provision at RIs
- Enhanced mutual knowledge and trust across the RIs domains
- Joint strategy across all RI domains on transition to remote access

WP5 collaborates closely with WP3 and WP4 to collect data to be used in communications activities, such as insights from WP3 consultations and use cases from WP4, i.e. studies on how specific RIs have implemented remote access.

Dissemination aims to communicate strategies and solutions to enable the transition to more remote and digital access to RI services. Discussions and events up to present (such as the first workshops in WP3) have highlighted challenges to a transition to more remote access, such as training – users do not have hands on experience and some technical aspects are difficult to learn remotely, or the issue of capacity and the difficulty of dealing with remote and present users. These will have to be borne in mind and addressed in the messaging. Figure 5 below details the targeted message for different stakeholder groups.

Stakeholders	Key messages
ESFRI clusters, projects and landmarks	<i>Open access to RI services, increasingly by remote methods, will bring benefits to accelerate scientific advances now and build resilience for the next global challenge which RIs will need to be ready to face with better preparation than pre-Covid.</i>
RI projects and networks	<i>Open access to RI services, increasingly by remote methods, will bring benefits to accelerate scientific advances now and build resilience for the next global challenge which RIs will need to be ready to face with better preparation than pre-Covid.</i>
RI technical and scientific staff - operators of instruments and equipment	<i>Communicating outcomes of use cases: real-world examples, communicating about database of solutions for digital and remote access. Seeking input for solutions for remote access for an RI that has little time or means to transition. Increased resilience is important to better face crises like the pandemic. Democratised access to RIs.</i>
RI IT staff	<i>In developing remote access to RIs, a key concern is to ensure data safety - seek input. Solutions on implementation of technical aspects of remote access. Communicate on the increased efficiency of service provision as a result of remote access. Provision of best practices and tools to lower the barrier to introduce more remote access</i>
RI user office	<i>Solutions on implementation of technical aspects of remote access. Expected impact: increased efficiency of service provision. Communicate that eRImote will provide best practices and tools to lower the barrier to introduce more remote access</i>
RI access managers	<i>Solutions on implementation of technical aspects of remote access. Expected impact: increased efficiency of service provision. Communicate that eRImote will provide best practices and tools to lower the barrier to introduce more remote access</i>

Stakeholders	Key messages
Users - researchers	<p><i>Raising awareness of remote access for the researcher who does not have access to an RI.</i></p> <p><i>Democratised access: RIs are more accessible through remote access, new user communities and new collaborations can be created. Remote access allows user to access to instruments and equipment previously unavailable to users, as wider base of RIs is accessible. Ecological impact.</i></p>
Users - students	<p><i>Raising awareness of remote access for the student who does not have access to an RI.</i></p> <p><i>Democratised access: RIs are more accessible through remote access: new user communities and new collaborations can be created. Remote access allows user to access to instruments and equipment previously unavailable to users, as wider base of RIs is accessible. Ecological impact.</i></p>
Users - businesses	<p><i>Raising awareness of remote access for the business who does not have access to an RI.</i></p> <p><i>New innovative solutions and collaborations between RIs and industry are possible.</i></p> <p><i>Democratised access: RIs are more accessible through remote access. Remote access allows user to access to instruments and equipment previously unavailable to users, as wider base of RIs is accessible. Ecological impact.</i></p>
Industry - Equipment and software manufactures	<p><i>eRImote seeks input from industry on available and emerging solutions to address technical challenges of remote access provision; eRImote can inform manufacturers about RI requirements for accessibility e.g. of hardware and integration into remote services</i></p>
Industry - data storage solutions	<p><i>Seeking input from industry to develop solutions for the technical challenges of remote access - specifically the importance of data and access security & the handling of sensitive personal and clinical data.</i></p>
Policy makers	<p><i>Recommend solutions that will benefit all stakeholders: the policymaker's involvement can maximise the scientific, technological, socio-economic and political impact of the project.</i></p> <p><i>Democratised access to RIs, resilience enabling scientific to react quicker to crises, ecological impact.</i></p> <p><i>Achieving joint strategies across RIs is more efficient (financially and societally) and allows more focus on improved scientific outcomes.</i></p>
Funders - national	<p><i>The funder can contribute to the European RI strategy so that the European landscape becomes more coherent, agile and attractive.</i></p> <p><i>Their involvement can maximise the scientific, technological, socio-economic and political impact of the project.</i></p> <p><i>Democratised access to RIs, resilience enabling scientific to react quicker to crises, ecological impact.</i></p>

Stakeholders	Key messages
Funders - European	<p><i>The funder can contribute to the European RI strategy so that the European landscape becomes more coherent, agile and attractive. Their involvement can maximise the scientific, technological, socio-economic and political impact of the project.</i></p> <p><i>Democratised access to RIs, resilience enabling scientific to react quicker to crises, ecological impact.</i></p>

Figure 5. Key stakeholder groups and messages for engagement and outreach

3.2. Outreach and dissemination activities

The dissemination of eRImote messages will be supported by a series of activities. These activities will all carry the purpose of raising stakeholders' awareness of the possibility of remote access to research infrastructures, and encouraging them to consider it, as well as enabling discussion around the advantages, challenges, and the future of remote access.

The activities will also have the aim for project staff to learn and gather input from the widest and most diverse range of stakeholders in the drafting of the Green Paper. Furthermore, the activities will lead to the final recommendations summarized by the project.

The activities shall be as follows:

- Four workshops on different topics:
 - o Environmental impact of remote training – co-organised with EOSC-Life and RItrainPlus projects (September 2022)
 - o Remote training for RI users and the impact on user interaction (September 2022)
 - o Remote operations of RI services and data and access security (October 2022)
 - o 4th workshop – in person in 2023
- A consultation sent to the target audience: December 2022 to May 2023
 - o Target: all stakeholders – as wide as possible from RIs themselves to existing users to the broader scientific community (not in contact with RIs so far)
 - o Aim: inform and gather opinions on remote use of RIs
 - o Format: survey (Google Form, SurveyMonkey, Indico)
 - o Questions:
 - Awareness of remote access to RIs, existing relationships, whether open to remote/digital use of RIs, what are challenges/advantages, what might be the future
 - o Timeline: consultation open for 6 months, December 2022-May 2023
 - o Outcome: responses gathered into different topics as defined by WP3
 - o “We will pay specific attention to balanced representation in the expert groups, to be inclusive of different perspectives, from different scientific domains, career stages and genders.”
 - o Coordination with WP3
- Meetings of five expert groups (EG) under WP3 to discuss specific aspects of remote access. For each expert group meeting, a summary of recommendations or key takeaways should be recorded and shared with WP5 to be included in the newsletter and social media campaigns. WP5: identifying experts to be involved.

The groups are as follows:

- o EG I: Researcher experience, sample handling, QA (INTERACT)
- o EG II: Data sharing, Data access and security (CESSDA-UKDS, CESSDA-ISSDA)
- o EG III: Remote training (Euro-BioImaging)
- o EG IV: Remote Instrument Control (Euro-BioImaging Bio-Hub)

- EG V: International access and accessibility (Instruct)
- Interviews and stories showcasing successful examples of remote access to RIs, linking with INSTRUMENT and DESY for the publication on the website and social media posts.
- Two conferences around 18 months after the project start – October 2023:
 - Why promote remote access to RIs
 - Why fund RI remote access operations
- A policy event at the conclusion of the project – June 2024
 - “The recommendations identified in the Green Paper will be the subject of a specific dissemination campaign, targeting the policy makers and funders on both the national and international level in WP5.”
 - Actionable pathways to support European RIs
 - Presenting the Green Paper to policymakers and funders.

3.3. Means

- Social media campaigns
 - LinkedIn, Twitter – to communicate all outputs and results. Twitter is mainly used for real-time updates and to promote event-centred activities, but also as a tool to engage new users/facilities. LinkedIn will be mainly used to onboard new stakeholders, send targeted messages and transmit news items such as success stories.
 - In January 2023, share stories about the demos in the third workshop.
- Newsletter: newsletter every 6 months in order to keep stakeholders informed on topics such as new initiatives, upcoming events and any other relevant updates related to the project.
 - In the first newsletter in January 2023, share the workshops report and the link to the consultation.
 - Dates: 2023 (January, July), 2024 (January, July, November).
- Websites e.g. <https://erimote.eu> & project member websites
 - Press releases announcing the project events, results, and information
 - Publish stories about successful implementation of remote access, the summaries of activities so far (e.g. workshops report)
- Visual identity and branding
 - Project logo and project templates – posters, presentations, documents, etc, ensuring uniformity and brand knowledge of eRImote to third parties.
- Promotional material brochures, leaflets, posters: virtual with QR codes.

3.4. Timeline

Stakeholder Outreach and Dissemination Plan

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Figure 6. Schematic overview of outreach and dissemination process for eRIMOTE

Annex 1 – ESFRI and H2020 RI projects

Infrastructure name	Status	Domain	Field	Link to catalogue
ACTRIS	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - landmark	Environmental Sciences	Observation of Aerosol, Clouds and Trace Gases	https://www.actris.eu/catalogue-of-services
AHEAD2020	H2020 Adv. Community	Physical Sciences	Astrophysics	
AnaEE	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - landmark	Health and Food	Experimentation on ecosystems	https://www.anaee.eu/services
AQUACOSM	H2020 Adv. Community	Environmental Sciences	Aquatic mesocosms	https://www.aquacosm.eu/transnational-access/
AQUAEXCEL3.0	H2020 Adv. Community	Agricultural Sciences	Aquaculture	https://aquaexcel.eu/transnational-access/
ARIADNEplus	H2020 Adv. Community	Humanities	Archeology	https://portal.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/search
ARIES	H2020 Adv. Community	Physical Sciences	particle physics	https://aries.web.cern.ch/facilities-offering-tna
ARISE	Other	Environmental Sciences	Atmospheric dynamics	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/284387
ASCENTplus	H2020 Adv. Community	Engineering and technology	nanotechnology	https://www.ascent.network/access/facilities/
ASSEMBLE Plus	H2020 Adv. Community	Biological Sciences	Marine biology	http://www.assembleplus.eu/access/transnational-access
BBMRI-ERIC	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - landmark	Life Sciences	Biobanking	https://www.bbmri-eric.eu/services-support/
BRISK II	H2020 Adv. Community	Engineering and technology	biofuels	https://brisk2.eu/facilities/
CALIPSOplus	H2020 Adv. Community	Physical Sciences	laser physics	https://www.wayforlight.eu/
CERIC-ERIC	ERIC	Physics (Photon Neutron and Radiation)	Materials, Biomaterials and Nanotechnology	https://www.ceric-eric.eu/users/open-access/
CERN	International Organisation	Physics (Astronomy and Particle)	Accelerator physics	https://home.cern/
CESSDA	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - landmark	Social Sciences and	Social science data archives	https://www.cessda.eu/Tools-Services

		Humanities		
CTA	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - landmark	Physics (Astronomy and Particle)	Gamma-ray observatory	https://www.cta-observatory.org/science/cta-users/
CLARIN ERIC	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - landmark	Social Sciences and Humanities	Common language resources and technology	https://www.clarin.eu/content/services
DANUBIUS-RI	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - project	Environmental Sciences	River-sea systems	https://www.danubius-ri.eu/
DARIAH ERIC	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - landmark	Social Sciences and Humanities	Digital arts and humanities	https://www.dariah.eu/tools-services/tools-and-services/
DiSSCo	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - project	Environmental Sciences	Natural Science Collections	https://www.dissco.eu/
EASI-Genomics	H2020 Adv. Community	Biological Sciences	Genomes	https://www.easi-genomics.eu/access
EATRIS ERIC	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - landmark	Health & Food	Translational medicine	https://eatris.eu/infrastructure/product-platforms/
EBRAINS	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - project	Data, computing and Digital Research Infrastructures	https://ebrains.eu/services	EBRAINS
ECCSEL ERIC	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - landmark	Energy	Carbon capture and storage	https://www.eccsel.org/services/open-access/
ECRIN ERIC	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - landmark	Health & Food	Clinical research	https://www.ecrin.org/activities
EGO-Virgo	Intergovernment consortium	Physics (Astronomy and Particle)	Gravitational observation	https://www.virgo-gw.eu/
EHRI	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - project	Social & cultural innovation	Holocaust research and remembrance	https://www.ehri-project.eu/online-course-holocaust-studies
EHRI-3	H2020 Adv. Community	Humanities	History	https://portal.ehri-project.eu/
EIRENE RI	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - project	Health & Food		

EISCAT_3D	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - landmark	Environment	Incoherent scatter radar facilities	https://eiscat.se/scientist/access-the-eiscat-facilities/
ELI ERIC	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - landmark	Physical Sciences & Engineering	Laser-based research	https://eli-laser.eu/
ELIXIR	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - landmark	Health & Food	Bioinformatics	https://elixir-europe.org/services
ELT	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - landmark	Physical Sciences & Engineering		
eLTER PLUS	H2020 Adv. Community	Natural Sciences	Coastal ecosystems	https://elter-projects.org/transnational-remote-access-ta-ra
eLTER-EUROPE	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - project	Environmental Sciences	Long-term ecosystem research	https://elter-ri.eu/
EMBRC ERIC	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - landmark	Health & Food	Marine organisms	https://www.embrc.eu/services
EMFL	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - landmark	Physical Sciences & Engineering	High magnetic field	https://emfl.eu/find-experiment/
EMP	H2020 Adv. Community	Physical Sciences	ultralow-temperature	https://emplatform.eu/about/facilities
EMPHASIS	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - project	Health & Food	Plant phenotyping	https://emphasis.plant-phenotyping.eu/EMPHASIS_pilots
EMSO ERIC	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - landmark	Environmental Sciences	Seafloor and water column Observatory	http://emso.eu/list-of-services/
EPIC-XS	H2020 Adv. Community	Biological Sciences	proteomics	https://epic-xs.eu/data-access/
EPN-2024-RI	H2020 Adv. Community	Physical sciences	planetary sciences	https://www.europlanet-society.org/europlanet-2024-ri/transnational-access-ta/
EPOS ERIC	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - landmark	Environment	Plate observing system	https://www.epos-eu.org/data-services
EPPN2020	H2020 Adv. Community	Agricultural Sciences	Plant breeding	https://eppn2020.plant-phenotyping.eu/EPPN2020_installations#/
ERIGrid 2.0	H2020 Adv. Community	Engineering and technology	Energy systems	https://erigrad2.eu/lab-access/

E-RIHS	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - project	Social & cultural innovation	Heritage science	http://www.e-rihs.eu/access/
ERINHA	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - landmark	Health & Food	Pathogenic microorganisms	https://www.erinha.eu/access-our-services/services-directory/
ESO	Other	Physics (Astronomy and Particle)	Ground-based astronomy	https://www.eso.org/sci/facilities.html
ESRF	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - landmark	Physical Sciences & Engineering	Synchrotron	https://www.esrf.eu/UsersAndScience
EST	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - project	Physical Sciences & Engineering	Solar telescope	https://est-east.eu/
ESTEEM3	H2020 Adv. Community	Physical Science	Electron microscopy	https://www.esteem3.eu/index.php?index=125
ET	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - project	Physical Sciences & Engineering		
EUFAR	Other	Environmental Sciences	Airborne research	https://www.eufar.net/projects/ta-application/
EU-IBISBA	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - project	Health & Food	Industrial biotechnology and synthetic biology	https://www.ibisba.eu/Our-Offer
EU-OPENSREEN ERIC	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - landmark	Health & Food	Chemical biology	https://www.eu-openscreen.eu/services/screening.html
EuPRAXIA	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - project	Physical Sciences & Engineering		
EURO-ARGO ERIC	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - landmark	Environment	Sea and ocean in depth profiling by floats	https://www.euro-argo.eu/Activities/Data-Management
Euro-BioImaging ERIC	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - landmark	Health & Food	Imaging	https://www.eurobioimaging.eu/service
EUROCHAMP-2020	H2020 Adv. Community	Environmental Sciences	Atmospheric simulation chambers	https://www.eurochamp.org/services

EUROFLEETS	H2020 Adv. Community	Environmental Sciences	Marine research vessels	https://www.eurofleets.eu/access/
EUROGOOS	Other	Environmental Sciences	Oceanography	http://eurogoos.eu/global-models/
ESS ERIC	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - landmark	Social & cultural innovation	Social surveys	https://www.europeansocialsurvey.org/data/
European Spallation Source ERIC	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - landmark	Physical Sciences & Engineering	Neutron source	https://europeanspallationsource.se/science-instruments
European XFEL	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - landmark	Physical Sciences & Engineering	X-ray free electron laser	https://www.xfel.eu/users/index_eng.html
EUSMI	H2020 Adv. Community	Physical Sciences	soft matter physics	https://eusmi-h2020.eu/access/general-information
EU-SOLARIS	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - landmark	Energy	Solar technologies	http://www.eusolaris.eu/
EVA-GLOBAL	H2020 Adv. Community	Medical and health sciences	infectious diseases	https://www.european-virus-archive.com/evag-portal-list
FAIR	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - landmark	Physical Sciences & Engineering	Antiproton and ion research	https://fair-center.eu/
GGP	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - project	Social & cultural innovation		
GUIDE	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - project	Social & cultural innovation		
HEMERA	Other	Environmental Sciences	Balloon-borne research	https://www.hemera-h2020.eu/
HL-LHC	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - landmark	Physical Sciences & Engineering	High luminosity large hadron collider	https://home.cern/science/accelerators/high-luminosity-lhc
HPC-EUROPA3	H2020 Adv. Community	Computer and informati	Computational science	https://hpc-europa.cineca.it/hostlist

		on sciences		
IAGOS	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - landmark	Environment	Observations of atmospheric composition from commercial aircraft	https://www.iagos.org/iagos-data/
ICOS ERIC	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - landmark	Environment	Greenhouse gas data	https://www.icos-cp.eu/data-services
IFMIF-DONES	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - project	Energy	Fusion materials	https://ifmifdones.org/
iNEXT-Discovery	H2020 Adv. Community	Biological Sciences	Structural biology	https://inext-discovery.eu/network/inext-d/services
INFRAFRONTIER	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - landmark	Health & Food	Functional genomics	https://www.infracore.eu/procedures/transnational-access-modalities/resources-and-services
INFRAVEC2	H2020 Adv. Community	Biological Sciences	Virology	https://infravec2.eu/vector-research-products/
InGRID-2	H2020 Adv. Community	Computer and information sciences	Databases social science	https://www.inclusivegrowth.eu/virtual-data-access
ILL	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - landmark	Physical Sciences & Engineering		https://www.ill.eu/users/new-user-at-the-ill/
INSTRUCT ERIC	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - landmark	Health & Food	Structural biology	https://instruct-eric.eu/platform-catalogue
INTERACT	H2020 Adv. Community	Environmental Sciences	Arctic research and monitoring	https://eu-interact.org/publication/interact-station-catalogue-2020/
IPERION HS	H2020 Adv. Community	Humanities	Heritage science	https://www.iperionhs.eu/catalogue-of-services/
ISBE	Other	Life Sciences	Systems biology	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/312455
IS-ENES	Other	Environmental Sciences	Earth system modelling	https://is.enes.org/ressources
IS-ENES3	H2020 Adv. Community	Earth and related environmental sciences	Climatic changes	https://is.enes.org/services-models-tools/
JERICO	Other	Environmental Sciences	Costal observation	http://www.jerico-ri.eu/ta/

JHR	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - landmark	Energy	Nuclear fuel and material	https://www.nnl.co.uk/innovation-science-and-technology/109-2/working-with-us-2/
JIVE	Other	Physics (Astronomy and Particle)	Very-long-baseline interferometry (VLBI)	https://www.jive.eu/european-vlbi-network-user-support-jive
KM3NeT 2.0	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - project	Physical Sciences & Engineering	Neutrino telescope	https://www.km3net.org/
LASERLAB-EUROPE	H2020 Adv. Community	Physical sciences	Laser physics	https://www.laserlab-europe.eu/transnational-access
LifeWatch ERIC	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - landmark	Environment	Ecosystems and biodiversity	https://www.lifewatch.eu/catalogue-of-virtual-labs
MARINERGi	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - project	Energy		
MARINET2	H2020 Adv. Community	Engineering and technology	Renewable energy	https://www.marinet2.eu/facilities/
METROFOOD-RI	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - project	Health & Food	Food quality and safety	https://www.metrofood.eu/
MIRRI	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - landmark	Health & Food	Microbial resources	https://www.mirri.org/mirri-services/
MYRRHA	Other	Energy	Nuclear research reactor	https://myrrha.be/
OPERAS	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - project	Social & cultural innovation		
OPTICON	H2020 Adv. Community	Physical sciences	Infrared astronomy	https://www.astro-opticon.org/h2020/tna/index.html
PRACE	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - landmark	Data, computing and Digital Research Infrastructures	High performance computing	https://prace-ri.eu/hpc-access/
RADIATE	H2020 Adv. Community	Physical sciences	Solid-state physics	https://www.ionbeamcenters.eu/ion-beam-facilities/
RadioNet	H2020 Adv. Community	Physical astronomy	Radio astronomy	https://www.radionet-org.eu/radionet/services/services-for-individuals/
RESILIENCE	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - project	Social & cultural		

		innovation		
RISIS 2	H2020 Adv. Community	Computer and information sciences	Databases	https://www.risis2.eu/risis-resources/
SeaDataCloud	H2020 Adv. Community	Earth and related environmental sciences	Geophysics	https://www.seadatanet.org/Products#/search?from=1&to=30
SEADATAN ET	Other	Environmental Sciences	Ocean and marine data management	https://www.seadatanet.org/
SERA	H2020 Adv. Community	Earth and related environmental sciences	Seismology	http://www.sera-eu.org/en/activities/access-to-research-infrastructures/
SFERA-III	H2020 Adv. Community	Engineering and technology	Solar energy	https://sfera3.sollab.eu/transnational-access-activities/
SHARE ERIC	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - landmark	Social & cultural innovation	Health, ageing and retirement	http://www.share-project.org/data-access.html
SIOS	Other	Environmental Sciences	Arctic earth observing system	https://sios-svalbard.org/Services
SKAO	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - landmark	Physical Sciences & Engineering	Radio telescope array	https://www.skatelescope.org/
SLICES	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - project	Data, computing and Digital Research Infrastructures		
SoBigData ++	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - project	Data, computing and Digital Research Infrastructures		
SoBigData-PlusPlus	H2020 Adv. Community	Computer and informati	Data science	https://sobigdata.d4science.org/catalogue-sobigdata

		on sciences		
SOLARNET	H2020 Adv. Community	Physical Sciences	Solar physics	https://solarnet-project.eu/Transnational-ACCESS
SPIRAL2	ESFRI 2021 Roadmap - landmark	Physical Sciences & Engineering	High intensity light and heavy ion beams	https://www.ganil-spiral2.eu/scientists/ganil-spiral-2-facilities/available-beams/
STRONG-2020	H2020 Adv. Community	Physical sciences	Particle physics	http://www.strong-2020.eu/all-activities/transnational-access.html
SYNTHESIS PLUS	H2020 Adv. Community	History and archaeology	History	https://www.synthesys.info/access/transnational-access.html
TRANSVAC 2	H2020 Adv. Community	Medical and health sciences	Vaccines	https://www.transvac.org/vaccine-development-services
VetBioNet	H2020 Adv. Community	Medical and health sciences	Emerging infectious diseases	https://www.vetbionet.eu/calls/
WindScanner	Other	Energy	Wind energy	https://www.windscanner.eu/

Annex 2 - RIs offering remote and mail-in access (MERIL database)

RI name	Acronym	Access
Abisko Scientific Research Station	Abisko	Remote
Alba Synchrotron Light Source	ALBA	Mail-in
AWIPEV Arctic Research Base	AWIPEV	Remote
Cellular Imaging Facility	CIF	Mail-in
Center for Cellular Imaging and Nanoanalytics	C-CINA	Mail-in
Center of Micronanotechnology	CMI	Mail-in
Centre for Mechanical Technology and Automation	TEMA	Mail-in
Coastal Ocean Observing and Forecasting System of the Balearic Islands	SOCIB	Mail-in
Cohort CONSTANCES	CONSTANCES	Mail-in
CRG Genomics Unit	CRG-GU	Mail-in
Czech National Corpus	CNC	Remote
European Research Infrastructure for the generation, phenotyping, archiving and distribution of mouse disease models	INFRAFRONTIER	Mail-in
European Very Long Baseline Interferometry Network	EVN	Remote
Experimental Facility for Ecology Research	ECOTRONS	Remote
INESC-Microsystems and Nanotechnologies	INESC-MN	Mail-in
Institute for Astronomy, Astrophysics, Space Applications & Remote Sensing (National Observatory Of Athens)	IAASARS-NOA	Remote
IRAM 30m Radiotelescope	IRAM 30m	Remote
Irish Centre for High End Computing	ICHEC	Remote
ISIS Neutron and Muon Source	ISIS	Mail-in
Marine Science and Technology Park, University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria	PCTM-ULPGC	Remote
Matrix and the SkyRa Platforms of the International Institute for the Advanced Studies of Psychotherapy and Applied Mental Health	PsyTech	Remote
National Institute for Earth Physics - Romanian Seismic Network	NIEP-RSN	Remote
PARADOX Supercomputing Facility	PARADOX	Remote
Partnership for Advanced Computing in Europe	PRACE	Remote
Portuguese Mass Spectrometry Network	RNEM	Mail-in
Satellite-based SAR-Measurement-System	TanDEM-X	Remote
Scientific Center for Optical and Electron Microscopy	ScopeM	Mail-in
Soufflerie Climatique Jules Verne	CSTB-SCJV	Mail-in
Swiss Muon Source	SμS	Remote
Urban Big Data Centre	UBDC	Remote
Westerdijk Fungal Biodiversity Institute	CBS-KNAW	Mail-in

Annex 3 - RIs offering remote and mail-in access services (CatRIS database)

RI acronym	Link to catalogue
ACTRIS	https://www.actris.eu/catalogue-of-services/services
ALM	http://www.cnb.csic.es/index.php/es/investigacion/servicios-cientificos/light-microscopy
ARL	https://www.arl-net.de/en/content/the-academy
ASTRID2	https://www.isa.au.dk/index.asp
AWI	https://www.awi.de/expedition/flugzeuge/polar-5-6.html
BayBioMS	https://www.baybioms.tum.de/
CIISB	https://www.ciisb.org/open-access/core-facilities/biomolecular-interactions-and-crystallization
CLARIN	http://www.clarin.si/info/k-centre/
CNIO	https://www.cnio.es/en/research-innovation/scientific-programmes/biotechnology-programme/flow-cytometry-core-unit/
COLLEX-PERSÉE	https://www.collexpersee.eu/a-propos/who-are-we/
CSHM	https://cshm.ac.cy/
DESY	https://particle-physics.desy.de/e252106/
EBMRC	https://www.embrc.eu/
ECRIN	https://marketplace.ecrin.org/en
ELETTRA	https://www.elettra.eu/lightsources/elettra.html
ELSA	https://joint-research-centre.ec.europa.eu/laboratories-and-facilities/european-laboratory-structural-assessment-reaction-wall-facility_en
EMMA	https://www.infrafrontier.eu/services/
EuroBioImaging	https://www.eurobioimaging.eu/service
Eurofleets+	https://www.eurofleets.eu/access/
EUROPLANET2024	https://www.europlanet-society.org/europlanet-2024-ri/transnational-access-ta/
FLASH	https://flash.desy.de/
Galaxy	https://usegalaxy.eu/

IBC	https://www.hzdr.de/db/Cms?pNid=1984
ICIA	https://icia.ro/en/servicii/cabio/
INFRAVEC2	https://infravec2.eu/vector-research-products/
INSTRUCT-ERIC	https://instruct-eric.eu/service-status
IQDA	https://www.maynoothuniversity.ie/iqda/data-training
JFYL-ACCLAB	https://www.jyu.fi/science/en/physics/research/infrastructures/accelerator-laboratory/
Lifewatch	http://ecoportal.lifewatch.eu/
LNCMI	http://lncmi.cnrs.fr/en/welcome/
MAPEX Core facility for Materials Analytics	https://www.uni-bremen.de/mapex-cf/instrumentation/3d-materials-analytics
NFFA	https://www.trieste.nffa.eu/
NKI	https://www.nki.nl/research/facilities-platforms/protein-facility/
NMR	http://www.slomr.si/sub_sites/general_info.php
PETRA III	https://petra3.desy.de/index_eng.html
PFBMI	https://research.pasteur.fr/en/service/characterisation-of-molecular-interactions/
PRACE	https://prace-ri.eu/training-support/best-practice-guides/
PSI	https://www.psi.ch/en/useroffice
RADIATE	https://www.ionbeamcenters.eu/radiate/
RISE	https://www.ri.se/en/ice-datacenter
Science-S.A.V.E.D.	https://science-saved.com/en/non-destructive-testing-analysis-2d-3d-imaging-analysis-x-ray-neutron-analysis
SIOS	https://sios-svalbard.org/RIAccess
SITES	https://www.fieldsites.se/en-GB
Sonnblick Observatory	https://www.sonnblick.net/en/
TEFOR	https://tps.tefor.net/
Wendelstein 7X	https://www.ipp.mpg.de/w7x

ZfP

<https://www.proteinanalytik.abi.med.uni-muenchen.de/index.html>

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